

LOWLAND TAPIR
CONSERVATION INITIATIVE

**PROTOCOL FOR AGE ESTIMATION
OF YOUNG LOWLAND TAPIRS (*Tapirus terrestris*)
BASED ON PELAGE PATTERN EVALUATION**

AUTHORS:

EMÍLIA PATRÍCIA MEDICI
FELIPE MORELI FANTACINI
RENATA CAROLINA FERNANDES-SANTOS

LAYOUT:

VICTOR HUGO SANCHES PEREIRA

**PROTOCOL FOR AGE ESTIMATION
OF YOUNG LOWLAND TAPIRS (*Tapirus terrestris*)
BASED ON PELAGE PATTERN EVALUATION**

LTCI - IPÊ
2022

PELAGE PATTERN CHANGES

DURING THE FIRST 12 MONTHS OF LIFE

WILD TAPIRS

INDIVIDUAL PELAGE PATTERN CHANGES

DURING THE FIRST 12 MONTHS OF LIFE

14 INDIVIDUALS (7 FEMALES AND 7 MALES)

WILD TAPIRS

15 DAYS

4 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

16 MONTHS

1 MONTH

4 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

14 MONTHS

17 MONTHS

1 MONTH

3 MONTHS

3 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

3 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

15 MONTHS

2 MONTHS

3 MONTHS

4 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

14 MONTHS

17 MONTHS

18 MONTHS

4 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

15 DAYS

2 MONTHS

4 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

20 MONTHS

21 MONTHS

21 MONTHS

25 MONTHS

2 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

15 MONTHS

16 MONTHS

17 MONTHS

20 MONTHS

50 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

2 MONTHS

3 MONTHS

4 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

15 MONTHS

1 MONTH

2 MONTHS

3 MONTHS

4 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

16 MONTHS

1 MONTH

2 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

5 MONTHS

6 MONTHS

7 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

8 MONTHS

9 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

10 MONTHS

11 MONTHS

12 MONTHS

13 MONTHS

INDIVIDUAL PELAGE PATTERN CHANGES

DURING THE FIRST 12 MONTHS OF LIFE

CAPTIVE TAPIRS

SÃO JOSÉ DO RIO PRETO ZOO, SÃO PAULO (BRAZIL)

1 DAY

36 DAYS

36 DAYS

74 DAYS

86 DAYS

92 DAYS

100 DAYS

107 DAYS

122 DAYS

128 DAYS

135 DAYS

142 DAYS

149 DAYS

157 DAYS

163 DAYS

170 DAYS

177 DAYS

184 DAYS

191 DAYS

205 DAYS

213 DAYS

219 DAYS

231 DAYS

233 DAYS

239 DAYS

240 DAYS

255 DAYS

261 DAYS

282 DAYS

290 DAYS

297 DAYS

303 DAYS

317 DAYS

324 DAYS

345 DAYS

353 DAYS

1 DAY

36 DAYS

36 DAYS

74 DAYS

79 DAYS

86 DAYS

92 DAYS

100 DAYS

107 DAYS

122 DAYS

128 DAYS

135 DAYS

142 DAYS

149 DAYS

157 DAYS

163 DAYS

170 DAYS

177 DAYS

184 DAYS

191 DAYS

205 DAYS

213 DAYS

219 DAYS

233 DAYS

240 DAYS

247 DAYS

255 DAYS

261 DAYS

282 DAYS

290 DAYS

297 DAYS

303 DAYS

317 DAYS

324 DAYS

331 DAYS

339 DAYS

345 DAYS

353 DAYS

**LOWLAND TAPIR
CONSERVATION INITIATIVE**

